

Open Letter

Observations on IPCC-AR6-WG-I: Scenarios of India & Ethiopia

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Abstract

An open letter was submitted to IPCC/UNFCCC/UN/WMO on “Comments/ Observations on IPCC-AR6-WG-I”. Don’t panic, Fundamentally Climate Change is “real” however Global Warming is a misnomer. To meet the political greed -- We plant one tree and kill/burn seven trees along with it the biological diversity within them – we are burning Nallamala and Shashachalam forests; We are destroying water resources by bringing down water holding capacity by around 60 to 70% and adding more sewage to rainfall and creating severe urban flooding as part of unplanned urban growth – bifurcation of states is part of this game only; We are destroying coastal zones by butchering/killing mangroves and converting the coastal CRZ for creating commercial hubs -- Vishakhapatnam coast line is a classic example. People are attributing all these human greed related causes to global warming. “Global warming of 1.5°C and 2.0°C will be exceeded during the 21st century unless deep reductions in CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions occur in the coming decades” -- This is the conclusion from the 1300 pages report of IPCC-AR6-WG-I and yet this is a qualitative statement as there is no standard climate sensitivity factor – except trail & error – that links greenhouse gases with energy with the resulting temperature raise. Also, the observed trend is not global warming – mainly adjusted component and land use & land cover component. Since 1960 carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is linearly increasing with population growth only. To get a glimpse of that future, scientists run experiments using computer models that simulate Earth’s climate. The IPCC uses a set of scenarios to try to understand what the future might look like but they present far from reality. That means IPCC helping wasteful expenditure and producing more air pollution and Carbon Dioxide. The IPCC doesn’t tell governments what to do. Its goal is to provide the latest knowledge on climate change, its future risks and options for reducing the rate of warming. The IPCC doesn’t conduct its own climate-science research. Instead, it summarizes everyone else’s. If this is so, where is the need to have a political body like IPCC, this can be executed by its parent scientific body, WMO, wherein all met services, who are more qualified in this area in the World, form part of it. Indian Scenario: (a) Temperature -- at state level showed increasing, decreasing and zero trends principally associated with changes in land use and land cover. Also showed increasing trend in night temperature – same is the case in China. No trend in Hyderabad, Sydney and USA temperatures. Heat-waves are principally associated with Western Disturbances based general circulation patters in India. Recent heat waves in New Zealand [June and July 2021 temperatures have gone up] and in Canada-USA also associated with general circulation patterns existing in those parts of the world. (b) Natural variability in Rainfall -- All-India rainfall data series between 1871/72 to 2014/15 for June to May rainy year presented 60-year cycle similar to Indian/Chinese Astrological cycle. This is seen in tree rings study in Brahmaputra River zone for 7 centuries [1309-2004] and water flows in Godavari River and frequency of severe floods in NW Indian Rivers also followed this pattern. However, in undivided Andhra Pradesh (i) annual rainfall showed 132 year cycle – water flows in river Krishna followed this pattern; and (ii) seasonal rainfall showed 56 year cycle. Southwest and Northeast monsoon rainfalls followed in the opposite direction – similar trend was noticed in Australian rainfall. The Bay of Bengal cyclones followed Coastal Andhra Southwest Monsoon Rainfall pattern. Added natural variability in Ethiopian rainfall – 36 & 28 year cycles are prominent.

Keywords: Climate Change, IPCC, UNFCCC, UN, WMO, India, Ethiopia

Introduction

Part-I: Indian Media

Don’t panic, the basic principal objective of IPCC’s latest report is to create sensation among nations and collect “Green Fund” -- \$100 billion per year for five years – and share it at the next COP26 meeting in November in Glasgow in UK. There is “NO” global warming. The word global warming is a misnomer. In Part-III I presented/discussed the real scenario of Climate Change with respect to India – added Ethiopian case in Part-IV.

- We plant one tree and kill/burn seven trees along with it the biological diversity within them – we are burning Nallamala and Shashachalam forests to meet political greed.
- To meet the political greed, as part of unplanned urban growth, we are destroying water resources by bring down water holding capacity by around 60 to 70% and adding more sewage to rainfall and creating severe urban flooding – bifurcation of states is part of this game only – see TS.
- We are destroying coastal zones by butchering/killing mangroves and

converting the coastal CRZ for creating commercial hubs to meet political greed and people are attributing this to global warming – example of Vishakhapatnam coast line.

- We got poor judiciary system in India that delivers judgments not based on law but based on political interests – for example recently APHC asked APPCB give advance information of their visit to the industry. This goes against the very purpose of surprise visit to check violations in control of pollution [air, liquid, solid]. The present Chief Justice of Supreme Court of India is following the footsteps of IPCC, we hear every day speeches after speeches.

We do bad job and we are attributing the associated ill effects to “global” warming, a fictitious index, a scapegoat. Let us set right our path and then talk of climate or climate change.

See my comments on earlier Reports of IPCC at Reddy [1-3] and online for 2013-14 reports.

Summary

1. I am working in the area of science of climate and the science of climate change since 1970s. Since 2013-2014 report, I have been submitting my observations on IPCC reports with zero impact.
2. Climate change is not global warming or vice-versa. Climate change is a vast subject in which global warming is a minor component – see WMO/IPCC/UNFCCC definitions. The IPCC reports are nothing but wasteful expenditure that contributes to air pollution and carbon dioxide. This causes diversion and wasteful expenditure to national institutions – to carryout time pass research.
3. “Global” warming is a fictitious value that serves the vested interests of UN Agencies and their “Cham-cha” institutions around the world who have no basic knowledge on the meteorology & Oceanography on the one hand and Agrometeorology & Agroclimatology on the other.
4. Several agencies around the world created “adjusted” global temperature data series [both surface & satellite] to show that there is a trend, but the trend are different. However, observed data series, for example Hyderabad in India, Sydney in Australia and USA presented “no” trend but showed natural variability – which is also seen in global average annual temperature anomaly time series [60-year cycle].
5. Natural variability in rainfall is seen all over the world wherein floods and droughts are part of them. All India annual rainfall followed Indian & Chinese Astrological cycle of 60-years – our fore-fathers followed this for agriculture and water resources planning. These are verified with 1309-2004 tree rings studies in Brahmaputra River zone.
6. Heat and cold waves are part of general circulation patterns existing in the respective zones/countries. Similar to Western disturbances scheme [my study in 1978] recent New Zealand and Canada-USA heat waves were associated with the general circulation patterns in the respective zones.
7. All ills of the societies around the world are associated with unabated population growth. The intensity of the weather based disasters has been multiplied with the population growth. The only remedy or solution is the population control. Can we do that???

Part-II: IPCC’s AR6-WG-I Report

1st Point

- IPCC's climate assessment since 1990 comprises three Working Group contributions: Working Group I (the physical science basis), Working Group II (impacts, adaptation and vulnerability) and Working Group III (mitigation) and a Synthesis Report. On 9th August 2021 released Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC) Working Group I report titled "Climate Change 2021: the Physical Science Basis", Though it is claimed that “The IPCC is the UN body for assessing the science related to climate change”, in reality it is not

science of climate or the science of climate change but the study relates to a fictitious global warming and its impacts.

- **The report claims that** “The Working Group I contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report addresses the most up-to-date physical understanding of the climate system and climate change, bringing together the latest advances in climate science, and combining multiple lines of evidence from paleoclimate, observations, process understanding, and global and regional climate simulations. This is false statement, there is no science but it is trial and error path.
- The SPM provides a high-level summary of the understanding of the current state of the climate, including how it is changing and the role of human influence, the state of knowledge about possible climate futures, climate information relevant to regions and sectors, and limiting human-induced climate change. Discussed under four headings, namely: A. The Current State of the Climate; B. Possible Climate Futures; C. Climate Information for Risk Assessment and Regional Adaptation; & D. Limiting Future Climate Change
- Global warming of 1.5°C and 2.0°C will be exceeded during the 21st century unless deep reductions in CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions occur in the coming decades.

This is the conclusion from the 1300 pages report and this is a qualitative statement and not based on science.

- The entire issue runs around there is increasing greenhouse gases and they are contributing to rise in temperature. However, since 2000 they are struggling to get a scientifically defined value for “Climate Sensitivity Factor” that defines the link between greenhouse gases and temperature by following trial and error approach with no real solution. This is the basic problem in IPCC approach of top to down as there are several variables with no clear cut values like cloud cover and water vapour.
- The greenhouse gases measurements started around 1960. The carbon dioxide concentrations in the atmosphere presented a linear increase with the population growth. This is clearly seen in Southern Hemisphere wherein less population, less carbon dioxide and lower temperature with less land area; and in Northern Hemisphere wherein more population, more carbon dioxide and higher temperatures with more land area – sea temperatures are less than of land temperatures. Humans inhale air use oxygen and release carbon dioxide. However, the basic issue is that carbon dioxide contribution to temperature in the presence of cloud cover and water vapour wherein they directly interact with the Sun’s Energy in raising the temperature.

IPCC claims that:

- The IPCC doesn’t tell governments what to do. Its goal is to provide the latest knowledge on climate change, its future risks and options for reducing the rate of warming. The IPCC doesn’t conduct its own climate-science research. Instead, it summarizes everyone else’s. This report – the first of four that make up the IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report – looks at the physical science behind climate change and its impacts.

If this is so, where is the need to have a political body like IPCC, this can be executed by its parent scientific body, WMO, wherein all met services, who are more qualified in this area, in the World form part of it.

- To get a glimpse of that future, scientists run experiments using computer models that simulate Earth’s climate. The IPCC uses a set of scenarios to try to understand what the future might look like. All climate models work a little differently and create different results.

That means IPCC helping wasteful expenditure and producing more air pollution and Carbon Dioxide.

- It is pertinent to mention here the fact on Himalayan Glaciers melt issue—IPCC says the Himalayan Glaciers won't melt by 2035 & expressed regret by saying that established standards of evidence not applied properly. Also, Al Gore withdrew his conclusion that “Greenland will become ice free in 5 years”. This was announced only after IPCC & Al Gore jointly received Nobel Prize. In 2014 a study of 2181 Himalayan Glaciers from 2000-2011 showed that 86.6% of the glaciers were not receding. This was informed to members of parliament in the session by minister concerned after his return from Paris meet in December 2015. This is the reality. Also unusually high snowfalls occurred in the last decade or so.

Fundamentally Climate Change is “real” but not Global Warming, which is a fictitious value that serves the vested interest groups to collect 100 billion dollars per year up to five years to share under the disguise of Green Fund.

Here it is pertinent to note that Climate is not static but it is Dynamic. Climate Change is a vast subject, in which natural variability is the principal component which was there in the past, is there now and will be there in future. This is beyond human control and thus needs to adapt to it. Our forefathers followed this in agriculture and water resources. Surprisingly Indian Astrological 60-year cycle and Chinese Astrological 60-year cycle follow this only.

The other component of Climate Change is human induced variations to climate. With the population non-linear growth, climate is affected at local and regional levels. Two broad components under this are Urban-Heat-Island Effect [noticed in London around 1800] and Rural-Cold-Island Effect that are related changes in land use and land cover.

IPCC/UN/WMO are talking on different components of human induced fictitious change, they termed it as global warming carbon credit policy. However, since 2007 [CMIP3] to 2013 [CMIP5] to 2021 [CMIP6] failed to get scientifically valid link, known as Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity [°C]. Here trial and error approach was followed with zero solution. They simply are harping on cloud cover and water vapour which are part of total solar energy (Rt) reaching the Earth's Surface and net radiation balance (Rn) at the Earth's Surface. They are localized and short lived factors with no accumulative impact. They maintain the Earth and Atmosphere temperatures at a given location- region and time. They are, however, modified by “Climate System” and General Circulation Patterns.

- Cube root of rainfall was found has a relationship with Rt & Rn and evaporation.
- Cloud cover and water vapour in the atmosphere related to rainfall.
- Cloud cover related to hours of bright Sunshine which in turn related to Rt & Rn.
- Rt & Rn follow sunspot cycle.
- Here we must remember the fact of vice versa is not a reality – temperature rise causing rainfall [4-9].

2nd point

“IPCC report highlights how climate change is causing extreme events and exacerbating risks of floods and droughts” By Aditi Mukherji (IWMI), Aditi is a Principal Researcher at IWMI and is a Coordinating Lead Author of Water Chapter IPCC's Working Group II, and a core writing team member of IPCC AR6 Synthesis Report.

Extreme weather events are increasing, and risks of floods and droughts are rising. In July, we saw catastrophic floods hit China, India and Europe. The ongoing famine caused by climate-induced drought in Madagascar

has affected over a million people. More people than ever before are experiencing climate change daily, and much of that is experience through water related changes. The new IPCC WGI report, which explores the physical science underpinning past, present, and future climate change, addresses some of the most critical questions of recent years. Are these extreme events linked to climate change, and are they increasing? Is climate change modifying the global water cycle? And what is causing climate change in the first place? Extreme weather events are increasing, and risks of floods and droughts are rising.

The IPCC WGI Report, approved at the plenary session on August 9th, drilled down into these questions. These are our top eight takeaways on water and extreme events based on the report's findings. Top eight takeaways on water and extreme events based on the report's findings:

1. The WGI Report reiterates what we have now known for a while: those humans are driving a rise in temperature, thanks to carbon and other greenhouse gas emissions. Currently, the global surface temperature is around 1.09°C higher than in the pre-industrial period (1850-1900), with stronger warming over land (1.59°C) than over oceans. Several of the climate impacts are already observed at 1.09°C, and these impacts will intensify at higher temperature levels.
2. Every degree of global warming is likely to increase global mean precipitation by around 1% to 3%. A hotter planet is a wetter planet because a warmer climate increases the moisture content in the atmosphere and feeds into weather systems, making wet events wetter.
3. The frequency and intensity of heavy precipitation events of the kind we have recently seen in Germany and China have increased at a global scale. This is especially true for North America, Europe and Asia, where long term observational data exists. Every degree of global warming will further intensify such extreme precipitation events.
4. As extreme precipitation events increase, so too will the frequency and magnitude of surface water floods and flash floods. This is because when there's high precipitation, the natural and artificial drainage systems cannot hold the excess water. As a result, a large amount of land is projected to be affected by river floods in the future, increasing with every degree of global warming.
5. A warmer, wetter world is also subject to increased evaporation leading to decreases in soil moisture and the likelihood of more droughts. For example, greater warming over the land surface reduces near-surface humidity on a continental scale, which contributes to drying at a regional scale. At 4°C of global warming, about 50 percent of all land areas will see increased frequency and severity of droughts. Even if global temperatures stabilize at an average increase of between 1.5°C to 2°C above pre-industrial levels, several regions, including South Asia, East, West and Southern Africa, will experience severe droughts. These also tend to be the places where a large majority of the poor people live and depend on rainfed agriculture for their livelihoods. Risks of forest fires also increase with temperature rise and droughts.
6. One of the most exciting scientific advances in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report is the high confidence with which extreme event attribution to climate change has become possible. Almost all extreme events that we have witnessed in recent years have been made more likely due to climate change. On a global scale, climate change is now potentially detectable from any single day of weather data. However, at a more regional level, the lack of long-term data in certain geographies limits the possibility of extreme events detection and attribution.
7. Most perennial rivers, including the ten major rivers originating from the Hindu Kush Himalayas, that provide water and food security to large parts of Asia, are glacier-fed. Yet, glaciers are melting almost everywhere. According to the WGI report, from 2010 to 2019, glaciers lost more mass than at any time since glacier mass balance observa-

tions began. This trend is only likely to intensify with every degree of global warming and will have severe implications on river flows, livelihoods, energy production and cultural values.

8. How we use our land and grow our food has also influenced the hydrological cycle. For example, water extraction for irrigation has affected regional water cycles across some of the most intensively irrigated parts of the world, for example in South Asia. At the same time, large-scale deforestation is likely to lead to increased runoff, and urbanization has increased local precipitation and runoff intensity.

In summary, all components of the hydrological cycle have been impacted by human-induced climate change, and the way we use our land and water has, in turn, also intensified the impacts. Many people in developed and developing countries are experiencing extreme events. Furthermore, given the current projections for greenhouse gas emissions, it is likely that we are headed towards a 1.5°C world by the mid-2030s, where most of these impacts will intensify further.

These are irrelevant to Indian context. They are hypothetical-rhetoric statements of pro-global warming groups.

Part –III: Indian Climate Scenario Temperature versus global warming

In terms of land area India covers one-third of China, in terms of population and irrigated area is nearly the same. The population of India covers 18% of the global population with 2.3% land area and as a result areas under forests have come down drastically. Mountain areas were destroyed for building railway tracks, roads, urban areas, dams, etc. Dry-land agriculture areas have been converted in to irrigate areas along with dams to store water from rivers. All these contributed to drastic changes in land use & land cover factor which contribute to “urban-heat-island” – heating -- effect and “rural-cold-island” – cooling -- effect.

According to IPCC’s AR5 [2013] report

- 1951 is the starting year for global warming.
- More than half of the trend is due to greenhouse [global warming and aerosols, etc.] effect.
- Less than half of the trend is due to non-greenhouse [land use and land cover changes] effect.

Global average adjusted annual temperature anomaly data series for 1880 to 2010 showed a trend of 0.6°C along with a 60-year cycle of natural variability varying between - 0.3 to + 0.3°C. Even if we assume 50% is global warming, then it is 0.45°C for 1951 to 2100. This is basically because of bringing down the values at the starting period of series, which was shown by the satellite data with no trend – this was later removed from the internet. So, global warming not real but natural variability is real both in temperature and rainfall. Global Solar Radiation and Net Radiation presented Sunspot cycle.

Indian temperature studies Recent study showed

- The state level temperature trend analysis showed an increasing, decreasing and zero trends following more or less the land use and land cover patterns.
- In India Punjab and the neighbouring zones showed decreasing or zero trend – in this belt dry-land areas were brought under intense irrigated agriculture with necessary development of water resources.
- Western Ghats full of ecologically sensitive greenery zone were destroyed to meet human greed in terms of real estate and introduction of commercial crops. This zone thus presented increasing trend in temperature at broader scale.

Another study showed

- Increasing trend in night temperatures – minimum temperature --. This is mainly associated with urban-heat-island effect – China also presented the same trend.
- Maximum temperature showed a peculiar pattern unlike minimum temperature.
- With this the average temperature showed 0.7°C increase. This has no relevance at local and regional scale studies. Soil type also showed large variations in temperature.
- During 2002 and 2009 presented deficit rainfall by 0.81 and 0.78% of annual at all-India level. This increased the temperature by 0.7 and 0.91°C.

Few other issues

- To meet human greed forests have been burnt or butchered. Present world data showed cut 7 plants along with the biological diversity in it and planted one plant. This resulted wild animals entering human inhabitations and crop lands. All over the world burning of the forests has the same motive in recent years.
- A recent report from the New Zealand suggests that June and July 2021 temperatures have gone up but they are not associated with the so-called fictitious global warming but it is associated with general circulation patterns/high pressure belts/circumpolar vortex, etc. existing at that time.
- Even in India heat and cold waves are associated with Western disturbances and associated general circulation pattern. In 1987 we presented such patterns.
- Recent heat waves in Canada-USA also associated with the pattern similar to Indian Western Disturbances. Unfortunately Official groups following the foot-steps of IPCC – simulation work.
- Huge hydro power projects have been coming up in Brazil & China that may cause cooling effect.

Power Generation

- New systems power generates huge waste with short life span.
- The so-called clean and green power – solar & wind – causes increase in temperature in the neighbourhood of the plant through advection.
- Brazil and China are building/were built huge hydro-electric power plants. They lower the surrounding temperatures but some argued they produce more greenhouse gases – forests will be destroyed
- Electric vehicles generate huge quantity of toxic waste that cause health hazards
- Nuclear power has several negative factors including storage of spent fuel
- It is essential to save the energy, reduce transmission losses, use of energy efficient equipment, etc.
- Stop expansion of unplanned urban areas by destroying fertile agriculture land for real estate ventures [3, 10-14].

Natural variability in Indian rainfall Past work

I started analysing the climate data for the presence or absence of natural variability since 1973 using the concept presented by [15], moving average technique while working under the supervision of Shri (late) K. N. Rao, a co-author of 1966 report “Climate Change” of WMO. I found 52 year cycle in dates of onset over Kerala Coast [published in 1977]. Later, studied the precipitation data of Mahalpe in Botswana and found 60-year cycle in 1981 [published 1981—ICRISAT/Hyderabad]. While working in Northeast Brazil [published in 1984], Mozambique [published in 1986] and Ethiopia [published in 1990] analysed the precipitation data series. In the last few years, UN agencies presented to media on droughts and floods scenario in these countries as global warming effect and media publicised them widely. But they are nothing to do with the so-called global warming

but they are part of natural variability in respective rainfall series. Some of these results are included in my 1993 book -- natural variability projections for four stations in Mozambique and South Africa were published in 1986.

Current work

IITM/Pune climatology group brought out a book on Indian rainfall at sub-division level (a) monthly, (b) seasonal and (c) annual for the period 1871 to 1994. I studied in 1996-2000, the southwest monsoon rainfall data series at all India level and southwest and northeast monsoons rainfall data of three met sub-divisions (Coastal Andhra, Rayalaseema & Telangana) in Andhra Pradesh.

All-India Rainfall

- At all India level, southwest monsoon precipitation contributed 78% of annual. I simply presented 10-year averages of all-India annual rainfall on a graph and found it is simply a Sine Curve of 60-year cycle – published in 2000 book. The frequency of occurrence of floods in few northwest Indian Rivers follow this cycle – published in 2016 books.
- Later I got annual rainfall data series of June to May for 1985-86 to 2014-15 used by Central Water Commission (CWC). By adding this to IITM data series showed clear cut 60-year cycle [same as southwest monsoon season rainfall] – two full 60-year cycles completed by 1986/87 and new third cycle started in 1987/88 – starting year of new year in Indian Astrological cycle [in Telugu calendar it is “Prabhava”], which is lagging by three years to Chinese Astrological cycle.
- Godavari River water flows followed this 60-year pattern only.
- Recently, a team of scientists conducted Tree Rings study to build Brahmaputra River flows for 1309 to 2004 [7 centuries]. They identified two 30 year drought years that fits in to below the average 30 year period of 2nd cycle [1957/58 to 1986/87] and below the average 30 year period before the start of 1st cycle [1835-66]. This clearly shows that there is no impact of the pseudo global warming on either in Indian rainfall or in water flows in Indian rivers.
- Indian parliament raised an important question: Whether Indian Rainfall is increasing or decreasing? The answer submitted to the parliament was: rainfall decreasing. This is false information as they selected 2nd cycle sine curve [1927/28 to 1986/87] starting with the above average 30 year period followed below the average 30 year period. By shifting 30 years forward or backwards, they would have arrived at “Indian Rainfall is increasing”. Indian rainfall has no trend but follow the cyclic pattern.

Cyclonic storms – Andhra Pradesh Rainfall

However, Andhra Pradesh rainfall presented a different picture over that of all-India rainfall. Andhra Pradesh receives rainfall in southwest monsoon [June to September] and northeast monsoon [October to December] and from cyclonic activity from pre-monsoon and post-monsoon.

- Southwest monsoon rainfall showed 56-year cyclic pattern.
- Northeast monsoon rainfall presented the same cycle but in opposite direction.
- The cyclonic activity during 1945-2000 during May to November presented similar to Coastal Andhra southwest monsoon pattern. Above the average 28 year period started in 2001. During above the average 28 year part showed more than 10 cyclones per year reaching as high as 16 storms per year with exception of one year; and during below the average 28 year period they showed less than 10 cyclones per year with majority of them around 4 cyclones per year reaching as low as zero. These are seasonal.
- Cyclonic disturbances in Arabian Sea and in Bay of Bengal [1891-1990]: The highest severe cyclonic storms occurred in May [pre-monsoon season/summer] and November [post-monsoon season/winter] in both the Bay of Bengal and Arabian Sea. These results clearly demonstrate the fact that temperature is not the driving force for the

occurrence of severe cyclonic storms in both Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal.

- However, annual rainfall data series of Andhra Pradesh [average of three met sub-divisions] showed 132 year cycle. Prior 1936, it was below the average 66 years in which drought conditions prevailed in 24 years [severe drought conditions existed during 1876-78 according to British Memoirs] and wet conditions in 12 years. The above average 66 years [1936-2001] period existed 24 wet years and 12 drought years. Since 2002 the 66 years below the average pattern started. Current data proved this pattern. The water flows in Krishna River followed this cyclic pattern.

Few others

- Another example is urban floods [not only in India but also world-wide]. These are the results of human greed. To meet that greed humans are filling the water storage tanks, rivers & rivulets and thus water enters on to the roads, houses. Here another problem is poor town planning to meet real estate business to amass wealth instantly. This is the root cause in Mumbai, Hyderabad, Srinagar, Uttarakhand, Kerala, Chennai, etc. Floods.
- However, ENSO [Southern Oscillation] showed some relationship with India southwest monsoon rainfall. ENSO has three parts namely, EL Nino, neutral and La Nina. During El Nino years we rarely get above average rainfall but during La Nina years we rarely get below the average rainfall. Neutral years have no such patterns [3, 10-14, 16-18].

Part –IV: Ethiopian Climate Scenario

A climate trend analysis of Ethiopia [Famine Early Warning System Network – Informing climate change Adaptation Series] study concluded that (a) Spring and summer rains in parts of Ethiopia have declined by 15–20% since the mid-1970s; (b) substantial warming across the entire country has exacerbated the dryness; (c) an important pattern of observed existing rainfall declines coincides with heavily populated areas of the Rift Valley in south-central Ethiopia, and is likely already adversely affecting crop yields and pasture conditions; (d) rapid population growth and the expansion of farming and pastoralism under a drier, warmer climate regime could dramatically increase the number of at-risk people in Ethiopia during the next 20 years; & (e) many areas of Ethiopia will maintain moist climate conditions, and agricultural development in these areas could help offset rainfall.

[19], studied annual rainfall data of 18 met stations with more than 25 years. The trend was fitted to sine curves. Table 1 presents the grouping of 18 locations according to climatic cycles.

Table 1: Grouping of locations according to climate cycles in Ethiopia

Periodicity [Years]	Locations
54	Koka (550)#
52	Gonder*(1150)
40	Moyale (680)
36	Gore (2250), Debre Markes (1320), Gambella (1250), Jimma (1450), Welkite (1220), Combolcha (1050), Dire Dawa (620), Negelle (790)
28	Jijiga (690), Wonji (780), Debri-Zeit (850), Bahir Dar (1450)
22	Asmara [now in Eritrea] (530)
Irregular	Addis Ababa (1210), Massawa (190)

* Cycle follows Catuane in Mozambique as 10-6+10/-10+6-10

Figures in brackets is average rainfall in mm

Natural variability patterns for four stations are presented in Figure 1

Figure 1: Cyclic pattern for four locations in Ethiopia

In general there appears to be a cyclic tendency in annual rainfall data of Ethiopia. The annual rainfall data of Ethiopia presents cyclic patterns of 22, 28, 36, 40, 52 and 54 years [Figure 1]. The border areas between regions of two different cycles present some irregular patterns, for example Addis Ababa which is border to 28 and 36/54 year cycles. Large part of the country is covered by 36 year cycle and next by 28 year cycle (Figure 2). The longest cycle is of 54 years at Koka in Shoa region while the shortest cycle of 22 years is at Asmara [now in Eritrea]. Bahir Dar presented 28 year cycle but Gonder presents 52 year cycle – it is similar to Catuane in Mozambique like -10+6-10 and +10-6+10 years. The prominent cycles 36 and 28 years (Figure 1), respectively are given at Gore, high rainfall mono model and Jijiga a low rainfall bi-model. The other cycles that are present in the southernmost part and northernmost part are 40 and 22 years (Figure 1), respectively at Mayole and Asmara. These patterns suggest that in a given year the chances of the entire country being under the below the average or above the average rainfall will be very rare. However, in 36 years zone wet to dry cycle changed around 1970/71 and in 28 year zone dry to wet cycle changed around 1962/63.

Figure 3 presents the altitude zones of Ethiopia. High rainfall zones with 36 years cyclic variation are seen in the high altitude zones. Crops grown in Ethiopia, more or less follow the altitude cum rainfall zones. However, tef, the staple food of Ethiopia is grown from low to high altitude zones with medium to high rainfall zones with not much difference in yield component. High altitude zones were not used for maize & sorghum. Low altitude zones were not used for potato, wheat & barley. Coffee is grown in high altitude with high rainfall zones.

Figure 3: Altitude Zones in Ethiopia

Figure 4 presents the seasonal march of rainfall and temperature for 7 locations representing 7 zones in Ethiopia. They vary from mono to bi-model seasonal patterns. The author of the article travelled on mostly gravel-stone roads all these areas in a truck with diesel drum at the back. Travelled parallel to Nile River [very deep like Godavari River in Telangana in India] that divides the Eritrea from Ethiopia; and visited coffee, barley, wheat, tef & sorghum growing zones. The temperature regimes in these zones fit with altitude and rainfall zones.

Figure 2: Natural variability pattern zones in Ethiopia

Figure 4: Rainfall and temperature patterns in Ethiopia 7 regions
 Note: Number in brackets refer to no. of years of rainfall data]

Tailpiece

River water sharing and interlinking of rivers will create future “Water War” crisis as technically unqualified Judges are appointed to tribunals. In the case of Krishna River Tribunal with unfettered powers to Judges did this. We are watching the same type of rhetoric with CJI/SC. In the case of Godavari River linking with Carvery River, Central Water Commission [CWC] with their over estimates model created the same. In both the cases the natural variability in rainfall factor was not taken in to account. Governments were least bothered on this as majority of them harp on non-entirety Global Warming.

Suggestions

United Nations must close down permanently Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC] & UNFCCC as the same can be carried out by World Meteorological Organization (WMO), basically because:

- They provide poor quality of scientific reports/work.
- They are good for nothing organizations and causes huge quantity of pollution and carbon dioxide.
- Provide funds to national meteorological services to build data on historical information on climate related issues to meet the local needs and clear the truth in the IPCC's reports.
- Natural variability in rainfall plays the major role in agriculture and water resources availability – these must be assessed country by country.

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